

Investigating the Relationship Between Librarians' Information Technology Training Needs and Service Delivery in Public University Libraries in Akwa-Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Purpose of the Study: *The study investigated librarians' training needs in information technology application and services delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.*

Methodology: *The correlational research design was adopted, with a population of one hundred and eleven (111) librarians from three (3) public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State. The total enumeration sampling technique was considered, while data was collected using two (2) sets of researchers' developed questionnaires. The questionnaires were validated by three (3) research experts and subjected to a pilot test using the test-re-tests method, which yielded a cumulative correlation coefficient value (r) of 0.87. Data were collected using physical contact with the respondents, which yielded a 91% response rate from 101 respondents who completed and returned of copies of the questionnaires. The data were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC), while the null hypotheses were tested using linear regression statistics at a 0.05 level of significance.*

Findings: *The findings revealed that librarians' training on institutional repositories application and Resource Description and Access application have a weak but positive significant relationship with services delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It also showed that librarians' training on library database management systems (LDMS) applications has a strong and positive significant relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.*

Recommendations/Conclusion: *The study recommended, among other measures, that university library management pay more attention to librarian training on key aspects of information technologies such as institutional repositories, library database management systems, and resource description and access to enhance effective service delivery in university libraries. It concluded, therefore, that training is indispensable in acquiring skills for information technology application and service delivery in university libraries.*

Study Type: *The study was an original empirical study*

Keywords: Training, Librarians' Training Needs, Information Technology Application, Services Delivery, Public University Libraries

Introduction

The evolving technological environment in which university libraries operate has made it indisputably mandatory for librarians to acquire new skills and competencies (Yusuf & Irenoa, 2019). This is quite necessary if librarians must meet new users' expectations and change the services of university libraries. Typically, changes in the university libraries occasioned by emerging information technologies in areas

of computer-based cataloguing, automated circulation systems, security management, online access to machine-readable bibliographic databases, as well as development and effective management of institutional repositories have brought about increasing needs for expanded skills, abilities, and knowledge of librarians. In other words, the application of information technologies in enhancing open access sources, user-centric services, including e-learning, e-teaching, e-information literacy, participation in webinars and online conferences, web-based library services, and the application of social networking are necessarily demanding commensurate training to enhance librarians' skills for effective and satisfactory service delivery. Typically, librarians' training is motivated by the university libraries' continuous drive for better and more value-added services, focusing on ways of improving skills, competencies and confidence for up-to-date performance. In this study, librarians' training is considered as the whole gamut of formal and informal activities, processes and techniques adopted by university libraries and librarians to improve and increase skills, capacities, aptitude and attitude of librarians for enhanced service delivery. Training could be accessed through education and learning opportunities in the workplace, using both external and internal processes, including observing how others perform certain tasks (Amisano, 2017). According to Oseji (2020), librarians' training refers to an organized planning process through which librarians learn useful technical and evolving skills to impart knowledge, develop skills, change attitudes and improve behaviour. It aims to satisfy the diverse information needs of library users through effective service delivery. Effective training of librarians impacts their abilities to acquire basic information technology skills for Internet searches, information retrieval, social communication and word processing-related activities for effective service delivery (Akwang & Udoh, 2024; Akpan-Atata & Enyene, 2014). It helps librarians deal with digital competency gaps in order to enable them to cope with digital information management, knowledge sharing, information security and privacy management, communication issues and other trending issues in library operations.

As a matter of fact, the need for effective training of librarians as an integral process of acquiring relevant skills and knowledge for the effective application of information technologies in delivering optimum services to library users to meet their information needs cannot be overemphasized. This is because effective training equips librarians with relevant skills for the application of information technologies for accelerated and efficient service delivery in university libraries. It practically helps librarians acquire the necessary and adequate skills and capacities to manage emerging systems such as institutional repositories, library database management systems, and resource description and access (RDA) for effective service delivery in university libraries. Training is necessary to improve service delivery in university libraries, which aim at satisfying users with a broad range of needs, which may be intellectual, social, and psycho-emotional, in order to achieve the objective of promoting learning, teaching and research. Meanwhile, in spite of the usefulness of training on librarians' ability and capability to apply information technologies for service delivery in university libraries, the actual needs for librarians' training are not usually streamlined or well-tailored, thereby making it difficult to achieve the intended goals of training, in university libraries in Nigeria. More so, librarians' training in most Nigerian university libraries is not often evaluated to determine whether or not the expected benefits of the training are achieved, especially as seen in the apparent poor information technology skills and service delivery among most librarians. Therefore, based on the above background, this present study investigated a correlational study of librarians' training needs in information technology application and service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study was specifically conducted to achieve the following objectives:

- i. To examine the relationship between librarians' training on institutional repositories application and services delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

- ii. To determine the relationship between librarians' training on library database management systems application and services delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- iii. To evaluate the relationship between librarians' training on resource description and access (RDA) application and services delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

Three (3) null hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance

H₀₁: Librarians' training on institutional repositories application has no significant relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: Librarians' training on library database management systems application has no significant relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

H₀₃: Librarians' training on resource description and access (RDA) applications has no significant relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Librarians' training needs

Training is essentially the process of improving, redefining or nourishing the knowledgebase, skillsets or level of capability of librarians in accordance with the changing operational and professional requirements of the modern information environment. Ghufli, as cited in Haliru and Sokari (2016), considered training as going beyond just acquiring knowledge and skills to increasing upward mobility within the university libraries and adjusting librarians to the technological changes affecting the workplace while focusing on attitudes required for performing and improving tasks more effectively for library users' satisfaction. Ongoing training provides great advantages such as improving service quality, decreasing labour costs, increasing productivity and performance, and more importantly, managing workforce diversity (Mathew & Zacharias, 2016). Training is quite necessary for the effective performance of the present job and for the acquisition of extra skills and knowledge for future engagement. It helps in providing capability, skills and expertise for technological advancements, competitiveness, collaboration and the changing learning environment, especially on issues bothering digital technologies and online communities (Akwang et al., 2024).

However, librarians' training needs are conceived as those aspects of librarianship practices in which librarians lack knowledge, skills, attitude, aptitude or confidence to effectively implement in a bit to deliver required services to library users (Isibika et al., 2021). Librarians' training needs must first be identified to effectively tailor the training to the specific areas of need for enhanced skills and knowledge acquisition. This implies that to ascertain librarians' training needs, questions like who needs training, what training is needed, why is the training necessary, when and where is the training taking place, what form is most appropriate for the training, and how long will the training take place, must be clearly answered. These answers provide appropriate planning and decision-making in order to guide the entire training process and bring about optimal training results.

Information Technology Application

Information technology is one of the most defining areas in librarianship, with strong implications for service delivery. Information technologies have gained prominence and a very significant position in the affairs of man across the globe (Chukwueke & Onuoha, 2019), as well as recognized as catalysts for change with great influence on every aspect of human activities, including library services (Adereolujo & Omole, 2021; Akpan-Atata & Enyene, 2014). Information technologies refer to a

variety of equipment, technological tools and systems comprising hardware and software used for information management in the areas of accessing, gathering, creating, storing, organizing, manipulating and disseminating information (Diane & Sebastien, 2020). The application of information technologies has brought tremendous changes and transformations in the ways that services are delivered in university libraries. This underpins the perspective of Agbo and Eyinnah (2022), who emphasized the relevance of information technologies embedded services and their application among librarians for the effective delivery of various library services.

More so, the application of information technologies in university libraries has greatly improved the speed, accuracy, effectiveness, efficiency, and quality of services delivered to library users by enhancing the ease of handling user's queries, information acquisition and sharing, as well as management of organizational procedures (Mensa et al., 2023). It helps keep pace with the latest developments, provides access to and dissemination of up-to-date information, and facilitates reformation and integration of information from diverse sources for enhanced satisfaction with users' needs. The application of information technologies eliminates repetitive work while bringing about innovative and creative ways of delivering services to user communities. It also promotes seamless and faster knowledge sharing among professionals for enhanced library service delivery. It, however, requires effective training and capacity building for enhanced acquisition of relevant skills and competencies.

Service Delivery in University Libraries

Service delivery in university libraries represents the core or prime essence of every library's existence. Service delivery can be used interchangeably with service provision. Service delivery in university libraries refers to the totality of efforts or activities provided and/or carried out by librarians using available resources and skills for the attainment of users' queries in order to meet the overall information, educational and research needs of library users. Oden and Owolabi (2021) defined service delivery as the ability of a university library or librarian to provide the information needs of users at the time of request to satisfy the expectations of users and improve their experience. Service delivery connotes the place, time and methods or procedures through which a service product is delivered to the customer, whether fair or unfair (Martins & Ledimo, 2015). It involves the assistance offered to a user who is searching for a given form of information within a particular library.

Service delivery in university libraries is primarily aimed at meeting the information needs of users who make up the university community to achieve the goals and objectives of promoting learning, teaching and research. Meanwhile, services delivered or provided in university libraries to users include user education services, circulation services, reservation services, interlibrary loan services, abstracting services, indexing services, cataloguing and classification services, current awareness services, selective dissemination of information services, reprographic services, bibliographic services, reference services, referral services, literature search services, internet services, among others (Akpan-Atata et al., 2014; Aloysius et al. 2022; Oden & Owolabi, 2021). These services can be delivered manually or electronically and require adequate skills and competencies.

Therefore, to deliver effective services in university libraries, librarians must be well-trained, especially in modern information technologies. This will equip them with the necessary skills, competencies, knowledge, attitude, and confidence for quality, effective, efficient, timely, and satisfactory service delivery based on users' changing tastes and preferences. Such training will also embolden librarians' perspectives on professional ethics, interpersonal relationships and communication with users. Effective training of librarians for service delivery will typically involve meticulous assessment and ascertainment of areas of need such as institutional repositories, library database management systems, and resource description and access (RDA). This will enhance their ability to effectively apply relevant

information technologies and approaches for improved user satisfaction and attainment of the vision, mission and objectives of the university libraries.

Librarians' Training on Institutional Repositories

Effective training is a sine-qua-non for the effective application of institutional repositories for service delivery in university libraries. Institutional repositories are platforms that facilitate the self-archiving of intellectual and scholarly content by scholars and faculty members for global visibility. Melo and Sanches (2022) conceived institutional repositories as devices that integrate and guarantee the operations of the Open Science movement, wholly supporting and/or encouraging the free circulation of academic and scientific publications by making available a wide range of information resources to academic communities and society. Similarly, Ware, as cited in Jelagat et al. (2020), defined an institutional repository as a web-based database or repository of scholarly materials that is institutionally defined, as opposed to a subject-based repository, cumulatively and perpetually holding a collection of records, open and interoperable using Open archive initiative-compliant software; and collecting, storing and disseminating scholarly information.

They are veritable tools for enhanced visibility and ranking of universities through access to the intellectual outputs of faculty members and affiliated research groups. Institutional repositories primarily aimed at increasing visibility, preservation and storage of all types of institutional output, including unpublished literature, support for learning and teaching, standardization of institutional records, ability to keep track of and analyse research performance breaking down of publishing cost and permission barriers, as well as help universities in shaping their knowledge and expertise (Christian, as cited in Akpan-Atata et al., 2015). Institutional repositories are essential elements of information technology, with vast potential for enhancing the possibility of disseminating and sharing information and knowledge within and beyond a university community.

However, successful and functional institutional repositories require deliberate and dedicated training of librarians who are saddled with the responsibilities of managing the hardware and software components as well as the scholarly contents of the repositories. Librarians' training in institutional repositories application is the process of acquiring skills and competencies for improved effectiveness in the use of institutional repositories. Training is a process that is aimed at improving the knowledge, skills, attitude and behaviours of employees to enhance their performance and accomplish certain organizational tasks and goals (Abubakar & Yahaya, 2024). Training librarians is essential if they are to become updated and versatile with trends, professional ethics and regulations, technological changes, and competitive environmental requirements through improved job-specific competencies and evolving workplace expectations. Librarians' training in institutional repositories facilitates the acquisition of technical and communication skills, knowledge of specific hardware and software tools, copyright regulations, open access issues and reporting requirements, as well as management skills such as planning and developing repository contents, evaluating repository performance, engaging in strategic planning, monitoring metadata quality and collaborating with stakeholders (Abubakar & Yahaya, 2024; Amadi et al., 2024). Training helps equip, empower, and enhance the capacity of librarians for the effective and efficient handling of institutional repository processes for quality service delivery in university libraries. It also helps in determining the quality of outputs to be deposited and to keep the repository functional and accessible to various categories of information users.

Librarians' Training on Library Database Management Systems

Another important area of librarians' training for effective service delivery in university libraries is library database management systems. Library database management system is an integral part of the advancement in information technology and essential for enhanced learning, teaching and research. A library database management system is a computer-based system that stores, records, and maintains

data or information in order to aid easy accessibility and retrieval for decision-making (Igere, 2022). It is considered by BasuMallick (2022) as an electronic arrangement that helps store data in a way that is not difficult to peruse, alter, erase, and scale, with the main goal of drawing relationships, controlling analysis, and supporting data-driven work processes. In the same vein, Obi and Nzerim (2022), as well as Udoh et al. (2023), posited that the library database system is a repository that stores reliable electronic information resources that are accessible by users through the library's dedicated access point. Library database systems convey information in various formats such as texts, pictures, images, numeric and alphanumeric (Obiano et al., 2023). Some of the examples of databases used to ease the organisation of information resources include Oracle, MySQL, PostgreSQL, RDM Server, Dbase, IBM DB2, GLAS, Apache, Informix, Access, and Ingress (Ijere, 2022). Library database systems enhance changes in data handling and efficient data processing while offering user-friendliness.

Library database management systems serve as part of the Open Access initiative, enabling librarians to modify, safeguard, and update information for the attainment of the mission and objectives of the university libraries, as well as providing opportunities for library users to access, retrieve and utilize information resources for their educational, information, research and recreational needs. Library database systems help to accelerate information and knowledge sharing within and beyond a particular university community. However, to effectively and efficiently manage library database systems, librarians must acquire relevant skills and competencies. These skills and competencies include basic skills such as operating systems, word processing, and computer skills, as well as advanced technology literacy skills such as knowledge of available databases, hardware and software installation skills, system administration skills, online, digital or internet search skills, troubleshooting skills, files management skills, etc. (Obiano et al., 2023; Udoh et al., 2020; Usman & Gopakumar, 2018).

Particularly, technical skills help in understanding and keeping abreast of metadata standards, security protocols, and user interface design to ensure a seamless experience for users. Acquiring these sets of skills and competencies by librarians requires effective and tailor-made training. Training in this context involves developing the capacity of librarians to enable them to understand compatible IT tools and software and regularly update databases, including subscription, negotiation and financial implications. Librarians' training in library database management systems also helps in understanding licensing and copyright issues for optimizing and promoting the quick discovery of information resources for users and managing huge collections. Meanwhile, the need for training librarians on library database management systems was emphasized by Chowdhury, as cited in Ijere (2022), as well as Inyang and Mngutayo (2018), who stated that operating database management systems in most libraries have been seriously hampered by lack of skilled personnel and competent professionals, as database management system can only be functional with workable software-hardware and experienced personnel.

Librarians' Training on Resource Description and Access (RDA)

Librarians' training on resource description and access (RDA) is quite propelling and momentous. This is because most Nigerian university libraries have yet to adopt the RDA in their cataloguing tasks since it was launched in June 2010 and implemented by libraries in advanced countries such as the American Library Association (ALA), Canadian Federation of Library Associations (CFLA) and Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals (CILIP) in 2013. Resource description and access (RDA) is conceived as a bundle of instructions, advice and data elements based on the Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR) and Functional Requirements for Authority Data (FRAD) that provide semantics of well-structured metadata and help users to access and retrieve data in the library world (Ahonsi, 2014; John-Okeke, 2019; Madukoma et al., 2023; Omosekejimi et al., 2022). Specifically, Madukoma et al. (2023) described resource description and access (RDA) as metadata creation and management, which is vital in managing resource discovery for both librarians and library users. RDA is a web-based cataloguing guide that is available on the Internet, where the

content is more electronic. It is developed in line with a set of objectives and principles, which are informed by the statement of international cataloguing principles (ICP). RDA is built on AACR2 structures but has its own distinct and novel characteristics that make it a better standard for cataloguing used by modern libraries. It is designed to assist library users in searching for different and specific information in the bibliographic record.

Resource description and access (RDA) provides a comprehensive set of general instructions and guidelines that are logically defined, easier to use, and more adaptable in describing all types of resources designed for the digital and non-digital environment while simplifying cataloguing rules and minimising special rules for describing specific kinds of materials (Tosaka & Park, as cited in John-Okeke, 2019). RDA is a highly technology-related cataloguing toolkit, an integrated browser-based online product that allows users to interact with a collection of cataloguing documents and resources. Its main aim is to provide a set of guidelines and instructions for formulating data to support resource discovery while allowing for the visibility of institutions through the shareability of information. Effective implementation of RDA requires a high level of skills and competencies in information technologies, especially internet-related skills such as browsing skills, as well as database and software application and manipulation skills.

Acquiring the expected skills for the use of resource description and access (RDA) is dependent on effective, conscious and regular training opportunities, which may take the form of webinars, workshops, seminars, conferences, discussions by librarians knowledgeable in RDA; visits to libraries using RDA; correspondence or online training via YouTube; in-house training, train the trainer programmes; offline training with downloaded training manuals and online distance education; webcasts, podcasts and RSS feeds (Mansor & Ramdzan 2014; Ahonsi 2014). In fact, the need for librarians' training on RDA underscores the assertions of Haliru and Sokari (2016), Oguntayo and Adeleke (2016), as well as Atilgan et al. (2014), who harped on training issues as the single most paramount concern for working cataloguers in preparing for the implementation of RDA. This, therefore, implies that effective training of librarians enhances their capacity to acquire a variety of skills and confidence, including internet-related skills such as mark-up languages, metadata development, tagging and multimedia indexing, user interface development and maintenance of the system. It also equips librarians with skills in data mining and database management, an adequate understanding of search engines like Google, as well as proficiency in the use of Boolean logic and the use of online cataloguing tools for effective application of RDA in services delivery in the university libraries.

Meanwhile, studies indicated that librarians' training in various areas of application of information technologies for effective service delivery is affected by several factors. Oseji (2020) reported that despite the rapid advancement in information technologies and need for training, training programmes in Nigerian university libraries are confronted with shortfalls in many areas, such as the choice of appropriate specialized courses, advanced studies, proper training opportunities and lack of proper training archetype for trainers and trainees. This was corroborated by Baro et al. (2019), who identified a lack of funds allocated to support library professionals' training, a lack of adequate physical facilities, and a shortage of skilled ICT educators as some of the challenges limiting librarians in acquiring digital literacy skills. Other obstacles to librarian's training in information technology application for service delivery include adequate technical manpower, lack of individualised training sessions, lack of entry behaviour test before training, low perceived behavioural control, lack of sufficient motivation of trainees, poor execution of training curriculum, inadequate training duration, lack of sustainability of training programmes, and lack of evaluation of training outcome.

Furthermore, Abubakar and Yahaya (2024) investigated the competencies and training of academic librarians for the management of institutional repositories in federal university libraries in North-East Nigeria. The study revealed that they possess the skills needed to manage institutional repositories in

the libraries, which enable them to install computer programs, use Microsoft Office and packages, and download and retrieve databases. It showed that they received training on the management of institutional repositories from their institutions and through personal training sponsorship at conferences, workshops, etc. The study indicated that there is a positive statistical relationship between librarians' competencies through training and challenges experienced in the development of institutional repositories in federal university libraries in Northeast Nigeria. Similarly, Olaniyi (2024) examined the effect of staff training on information services delivery to library users in public libraries in South-West Nigeria. The study revealed that there is a positive and significant linear relationship between staff training and information service delivery to users in public libraries, even though staff in public libraries are not often exposed to training. It showed that the most frequently used training methods in libraries include workshops, seminars, conferences, job rotation, mentoring or coaching, research training, etc. They found out that lack of funds for organising training programmes, poor budgetary allocation to public libraries, lack of written training development policies, inadequate knowledge of ICT facilities, and lack of necessary training facilities are the main hindrances to training in public libraries. It was recommended that public libraries pay attention to staff training and development by investing the required resources that will enable the library staff and institutions to maximise the benefits of training and development.

In a related study, Obim (2023) examined the staff training needs of librarians for effective library service delivery in Nigerian university libraries during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. The study found that the major staff training needs of librarians include training on the effective adoption of digital or virtual reference services, training on how to use Zoom for library service, training on effective implementation of electronic resources to delivery service, training on how to migrate to web-based library services, training on the adoption of social networking and web 2.0 technologies for library services, etc. It also showed that library staff received training through in-house training, online conferences, seminars and workshops, and online courses. It identified inadequate technological facilities to organise in-house staff training, lack of funds, lack of staff training policy, and nonchalant attitude of library management towards sponsoring the training of staff as the major challenges inhibiting the training of staff for effective service delivery in university libraries.

Obiano et al. (2023) investigated the application of library database management systems in university libraries in South-Eastern Nigeria. The study revealed that the proportion of university libraries that adopt library database management systems is low and less encouraging and that academic libraries in federal universities make use of library database management systems more than academic libraries in state universities. It attributed the poor level of application of library database management systems in the university libraries to poor funding and lack of staff training in academic libraries in order to adopt library database management systems. Based on the findings, the study recommended that academic libraries, both federal and state, should be funded properly, and staff should be trained to adhere to global services obtained in academic libraries by adopting library database management systems and shifting away from traditional print materials. Omoosejimi et al. (2022) equally examined cataloguers' awareness, ICT skills and use of resource description and access (RDA) in university libraries in South-South Nigeria. The study revealed that cataloguers in university libraries in South-South Nigeria were aware of the existence of RDA. Still, the extent of cataloguers' awareness of RDA in university libraries was low. It showed that the librarians lacked basic ICT skills, such as the ability to use the Windows operating system, Macintosh operating system, and Disk Operating System (DOS) commands to apply RDA in service delivery. It indicated that the librarians the extent of the use of RDA for cataloguing information resources in university libraries in South-South, Nigeria is very low and that the libraries and librarians lack requisite ICT facilities and necessary RDA-related training, as well as lack of familiarity with RDA rules and guidelines and lack access to RDA toolkit. The study recommended

that library management should adopt and implement the process of RDA in university libraries as well as create awareness about the functions and usefulness of RDA in the services of the university libraries. Isibika et al. (2021) investigated the perceived training needs assessment of librarians in Tanzanian academic libraries aimed at introducing microlearning intervention to training. The study indicated that librarians require a high level of training to enhance their ICT and technical skills, especially in database management, website designing, advanced search, information storage and retrieval, and information organisation and storage, among others. It was found that adequate training can benefit librarians by keeping them up to date with new trends in the profession and helping them build their capacity to effectively respond to users' changing needs and preferences in libraries. The study further identified a lack of transparency and fairness in selecting employees for training, a lack of prospects for training, and a lack of supportive organisational culture as some of the major barriers to the training needs of librarians.

In another similar study, Oden and Owolabi (2021) examined staff attitude and service delivery in university libraries in Ogun State, Nigeria. The study revealed that staff attitude had a significant influence on service delivery since library staff delivered quality services in university libraries by demonstrating a positive attitude toward the users. It recommended that the university library board and administrators should employ qualified library staff with the right disposition that can evaluate and assess users' needs regularly, be compassionate to users' needs and display the right disposition in any condition toward users in order to increase patronage.

Jelagat et al. (2020) investigated the role of librarians in the use of institutional repositories in higher learning institutions in Kenya. The study revealed that globally, most universities have embraced institutional repositories. Still, the unawareness of librarians of their roles and low technical skills in the use of institutional repositories have been incriminated for low visibility of research output, notwithstanding the many research activities undertaken by universities. It showed that academic librarians have not played their roles in institutional repositories as extensively as expected due to poor training and requisite skills.

In another related survey on resource description and access (RDA), the training needs of librarians in university libraries in northwestern Nigeria were reported. Haliru and Sokari (2016) reported that the level of RDA skills of librarians was very low. The study found that librarians greatly require training in all aspects of RDA. It is recommended that librarians should be trained on the use of RDA for cataloguing, particularly in the areas where they lack the technical know-how, such as in the use of the internet, development of metadata, and tagging. It is also recommended that university library management solicit support from TETFund in order to roll out the training and purchase RDA toolkits. To the researcher's knowledge, no study was conducted on librarians' training needs in information technology applications for service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, from the above studies. Thus, this study was carried out to fill the observed gap in the literature.

Methodology

This study adopted a correlational research design to investigate librarians' training needs and information technology applications for service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The population consisted of one hundred and eleven (111) librarians from three (3) public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, comprising 26 from Akwa Ibom State University (AKSU) Library, 5 from Federal University of Technology, Ikot Abasi (FUTIA) Library and 80 from University of Uyo (UNIUYO) Library. These university libraries were considered due to their strategic status and the need to establish how well they prioritize librarians' training in information technology applications for enhanced service delivery. Only professional staff, that is, those with Bachelor, Master and PhD degrees in Library and Information Science, were considered for the study. The total enumeration sampling technique was used since the study population was manageable. Data for the study were

collected using two (2) sets of researchers' developed questionnaires with structured questions for the independent and dependent variables. The two (2) sets of questionnaires were validated by three (3) research experts from Library and Information Science and Measurement and Evaluation disciplines from Akwa Ibom State University. The data collected were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC), while the null hypotheses were tested using linear regression statistics at a 0.05 level of significance. The degree of relationship of the variables was determined and interpreted using Creswell's (2014) correlation coefficient scale, which holds that correlation coefficient (r) $\pm 0.00 - 0.20$ = very low relationship, $\pm 0.21 - 0.40$ = low relationship, $\pm 0.41 - 0.60$ = moderate relationship, $\pm 0.61 - 0.80$ = high relationship, while $\pm 0.81 - 1.00$ = very high relationship. Also, the decision rule for rejecting or accepting the null hypothesis was to reject the null hypothesis if the p-value is less than the alpha value at 0.05 level of significance or otherwise accept it.

Results and Discussion of Findings

The results of this study were presented in tables according to the specific objectives and corresponding hypotheses, and interpretations were provided accordingly.

Research Objective 1: To Examine the Relationship between Librarians' Training on Institutional Repositories Application and Services Delivery in Public University Libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between Librarians' Training on Institutional Repositories Application and Services Delivery in Public University Libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

		LTIRA	SDPUL
LTIRA	Pearson's Correlation Sig. (2tailed)	1	0.032
	N	101	101
SDPUL	Pearson's Correlation Sig. (2tailed)	0.032	1
	R ²	0.001	
	N	101	101

KEYS: *LTIRA* = Librarians' Training on Institutional Repositories Application

SDPUL = Services Delivery in Public University Libraries

Data in Table 1 revealed that there was a very low extent of correlation between librarians' training on Institutional Repository (IR) application and services delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, as indicated by the correlation coefficient ($r = 0.032$) which is positive and falls within the coefficient limit of $\pm 0.00 - 0.20$. The coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.001$) indicates that 10% of the variance observed in service delivery in public university libraries is accounted for by librarians' training on Institutional Repository application. This implies that librarians' training on Institutional Repository (IR) application, to a very low but positive extent, correlates with service delivery in the public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1: Librarians' training on institutional repository application has no significant relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

Table 2: Simple regression analysis of the relationship between librarians’ training on Institutional Repositories application and services delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

<i>Model</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Sum of Square</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Regression	1	2.088	2.088	0.122	0.728
Residual	99	1696.209	17.133		
Total	100	1698.297			

Data in Table 2 above showed a p-value of 0.0728, which is numerically greater than the alpha value of 0.05 but not statistically strong enough to cause a rejection of the null hypothesis. Thus, since the p-value of 0.728 was not statistically strong enough to cause a rejection of the null hypothesis, it was concluded that librarians’ training on institutional repositories application has a weak but positive relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The findings of the study, as shown in Tables 1 and 2 above, revealed that librarians’ training on institutional repository application has a weak but positive relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This indicated that librarians have not received adequate training on the application of institutional repositories (IR) for service delivery, notwithstanding the fact that institutional repository application has a strong positive significance on service delivery in public university libraries. The finding agrees with Jelagat et al. (2020), who examined the role of librarians in the use of institutional repositories in higher learning institutions in Kenya and discovered that though most universities have embraced institutional repositories low technical skills due to poor training is hindering librarians in the use of institutional repository for enhancing the visibility and services of the universities. It, however, disagrees with Abubakar and Yahaya (2024), who investigated the competencies and training of academic librarians for the management of institutional repositories in federal university libraries in North-East Nigeria and found that there is a positive statistical relationship between librarians’ competencies through training and challenges experienced in the development of institutional repositories in federal university libraries in Northeast Nigeria. From the above findings, it was deduced that deliberate efforts, decisions, investment and commitment are needed by both management of public university libraries and librarians toward enhancing training and capacity building on institutional repositories as essential components of information technology for effective service delivery and promotion of information management processes for the satisfaction of users’ needs in the university libraries.

Research Objective 2: To Determine the Relationship between Librarians’ Training on Library Database Management Systems (LDMS) Application and Services Delivery in Public University Libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between Librarians’ Training on Library Database Management Systems (LDMS) Application and Services Delivery in Public University Libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

		<i>LTLDMSA</i>	<i>SDPUL</i>
<i>LTLDMSA</i>	Pearson’s Correlation Sig. (2tailed)	1	0.230
	N	101	101
<i>SDPUL</i>	Pearson’s Correlation Sig. (2tailed)	0.230	1

	R ²	0.053	
	N	101	101

KEYS: *LTLDMSA* = Librarians’ Training on Library Database Management Systems Application
SDPUL = Services Delivery in Public University Libraries

Data in Table 3 showed that there was a low extent of correlation between librarians’ training on library database management systems (LDMS) application and services delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, as indicated by the correlation coefficient ($r = 0.230$) which is positive and falls within the coefficient limit of $\pm 0.21 - 0.40$. The coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.053$) indicates that 53% of the variance observed in service delivery in public university libraries is accounted for by librarians’ training on library database management systems application. This implies that librarians’ training on library database management systems (LDMS) application, to a low but positive extent, correlates with service delivery in the public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

H0₂: Librarians’ training on library database management systems application has no significant relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

Table 4: Simple regression analysis of the relationship between librarians’ training on library database management systems application and services delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

<i>Model</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Sum of Square</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Regression	1	38.073	38.073	5.255	0.024
Residual	99	717.234	7.245		
Total	100	755.307			

Data in Table 4 above showed a p-value of 0.024, which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Thus, since the p-value of 0.024 is less than the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis, which states that librarians’ training on library database management systems application has no significant relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in South-South, Nigeria, was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was accepted. Thus, it was concluded that librarians’ training in library database management systems application has a strong and positive significant relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The findings of the study indicated in Tables 3 and 4 show that librarians’ training on library database management systems (LDMS) application has a strong and significant positive relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It implies that librarians have received moderate training and acquired relevant skills on how to apply or work with library database management systems by managing subscription, licensing and copyright issues for effective service delivery in the university libraries. The finding partly disagrees with Obiano et al. (2023), who studied the application of library database management systems in university libraries in Southeast Nigeria and found that the proportion of university libraries that apply library database management systems was low due to a lack of staff training in the libraries. On the other hand, the finding corroborates with Isibika et al. (2021), who investigated the perceived training needs assessment of librarians in Tanzanian academic libraries and discovered that librarians require high level of training to enhance their ICT and technical skills in areas of database management, website designing, and advanced search since adequate training benefits librarians by keeping them up to date with new trends in the profession and helping them to build their capacity to effectively respond to users’ changing needs and preferences in

the libraries. This finding typically harps on more training of librarians on library database management systems as a strong element of information technology application for effective and satisfactory service delivery in university libraries.

Research Objective 3: To evaluate the relationship between librarians' training on resource description and access (RDA) application and services delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between Librarians' Training on Resource Description and Access (RDA) Application and Services Delivery in Public University Libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

		LTRDAA	SDPUL
LTRDAA	Pearson's Correlation Sig. (2tailed)	1	0.166
	N	101	101
SDPUL	Pearson's Correlation Sig. (2tailed)	0.166	1
	R ²	0.028	
	N	101	101

KEYS: LTRDAA = Librarians' Training on Resource Description and Access Application
SDPUL = Services Delivery in Public University Libraries

The data in Table 5 revealed that there was a very low extent of correlation between librarians' training on Resource Description and Access (RDA) application and services delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, as indicated by the correlation coefficient ($r = 0.166$) which is positive and falls within the coefficient limit of $\pm 0.00 - 0.20$. The coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.028$) indicated that 28% of the variance observed in service delivery in public university libraries is accounted for by librarians' training on the Resource Description and Access (RDA) application. This implies that librarians' training on RDA application, to a very low but positive extent, correlates with service delivery in the public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

H0₃: Librarians' training on Resource Description and Access (RDA) application has no significant relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

Table 6: Simple Regression Analysis of the Relationship between Librarians' Training on Resource Description and Access (RDA) Application and Services Delivery in Public University Libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

Model	Df	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1	21.599	21.599	2.688	0.104
Residual	99	795.589	8.036		
Total	100	817.188			

Data in Table 6 above showed a p-value of 0.104, which is numerically greater than the alpha value of 0.05 but not statistically strong enough or significant enough to cause a rejection of the null hypothesis. Thus, since the p-value of 0.104 was not statistically strong enough to cause a rejection of the null hypothesis, it was concluded that librarians' training on Resource Description and Access has a weak

but positive significant relationship with services delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The findings of the study, as shown in Tables 5 and 6, revealed that librarians' training on resource description and access has a weak but significant positive relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This indicated that librarians had not received adequate training on Resource Description and Access (RDA) in the areas of general overview and structure of RDA, FRBR and FRAD, RDA rules and guidelines, RDA data encoding schema, RDA metadata and tagging, etc., for effective services delivery in the public university libraries. The finding negatively agrees with a survey conducted on Resource Description and Access (RDA) training needs for librarians in university libraries of North-Western Nigeria by Haliru and Sokari (2016), which reported that the level of RDA skills of librarians was very low. It also negatively corroborates Omoosejimi et al. (2022), which investigated cataloguers' awareness, ICT skills and use of resource description and access (RDA) in university libraries in South-South, Nigeria, and found that the librarians' extent of use of RDA for cataloguing of information resources in the university libraries in South-South, Nigeria, was very low since the libraries and librarians lack requisite ICT facilities, necessary RDA related training and basic ICT skills such as the ability to use Windows operating system, Macintosh operating system and Disk Operating System (DOS) commands to apply RDA in service delivery. Based on this finding, it was deduced that public university libraries and librarians in Akwa Ibom State have to take conscious steps to facilitate training on resource description and access as a fundamental component of modern information management systems in university libraries.

Conclusion

Librarians' training is an integral process of acquiring relevant knowledge, skills and competencies for effective application of information technologies. It is a fundamental requirement for librarians to deliver optimum services to satisfy library users' needs. In this study, it was revealed that librarians' training on institutional repository application has a weak but positive relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It was also discovered that librarians' training on library database management systems (LDMS) applications has a strong and positive significant relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study further showed that librarians' training on Resource Description and Access has a weak but positive significant relationship with service delivery in public university libraries in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study, however, concluded that the management of university libraries and librarians needs to give librarians' training on institutional repositories application, library database management systems (LDMS) application, and resource description and access (RDA) priority attention in order to enhance effective services delivery in university libraries.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations were made to enhance the effectiveness of university libraries. Firstly, it is suggested that university management should provide adequate funding to university libraries to facilitate the acquisition of emerging information technologies and the training of librarians, enabling them to deliver services more effectively. Secondly, university library management should prioritise training librarians on key aspects of information technology, including institutional repositories, library database management systems, and resource description and access, to ensure they remain current with evolving trends in service delivery. Lastly, librarians should focus on upskilling their capacity and knowledge of emerging information technologies and library services, such as resource description and access, to improve information management within university libraries.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors hereby declare that the research was carried out without any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest. They all contributed uniquely to the research from conceptualization to completion.